

Abstract

In this short contribution, we present a work-in-progress investigation on the morphology of AI-generated plays. To do so, we generate a batch of texts in different languages through GPT-3.5 and Bard, mark up their structure, and compare them to benchmark theatrical corpora. Eventually, we find out and discuss some distinctive features of artificial plays which help us to make sense of the models' inner workings, biases and more generally of their 'understanding' of drama.

The AI Playwright: An Experiment in Literary Morphology

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1 Background

The rise of Large Language Models (LLMs) has established generative artificial intelligence as a transformative technology with applications across various domains, including literary studies (see e.g. [14] [20]). In the field of drama research and practice, LLMs have been already exploited by projects dealing with experimental theatre writing, which have tried to embed them into the creative writing process. In most cases, their story generation capabilities have been leveraged to create scripts from curated prompts, such as in [12] [13] [8]. To our knowledge, however, no attempts have been made to use LLMs as a hermeneutical tool for investigating drama from a literary point of view – for example, comparing the features of AI- and human-generated plays to make sense of the models' inner workings, biases and more generally of their understanding of drama as shaped by their (largely non-disclosed) training sets.

The approach we are prototyping here, while novel, is indebted to previous studies which have played with the concept of 'simulating dramatic texts' before the spread of LLMs. A notable example is an experiment by Moretti and colleagues [9], whose attempt was however limited to one aspect of theatre plays, i.e., their character system. Thanks to a four-parameter network generation algorithm, their study recreated the structures of plays by Sophocles, Shakespeare, Racine, and Ibsen, measuring the hiatus between artificial and actual character constellations and trying to explain it with historical conventions or authorial decisions. By the authors' own admission, results were somehow inconclusive: the model they built implied "a complete subordination of history to morphology", losing sight of historical reality and focusing instead on the unsuccessful endeavour to build a "periodic table of [all imaginable] dramatic networks" (43).

While our contribution shares Moretti's focus on morphological traits, and more specifically on structural and formal aspects, we are not interested in making sense of literary evolution, but rather in assessing drama generation

performances of AI tools. To do so, we first generate batches of random plays using various LLMs and then compare them to human-generated texts from the DraCor database (<https://dracor.org>), a large multilingual repository of plays [5]. We choose to use plays from the 19th century as benchmark due to the absence of copyright issues; we focus on French-, German-, and Russian-language texts since the corresponding DraCor corpora have the largest text availability. As in other recent ‘quantitative formalist’ approaches to drama [16] [6], we direct our attention to textual features which can easily be quantified and extracted while, at the same time, conveying insights into the overall structure. These metrics, which we will review in detail later, are mostly related to the plays’ size, speech distribution, and character networks (with the latter being a recurrent theme in computational drama research, e.g. [18] [1]).

2 Experiment

2.1 Model choice and prompt design

For our experiment, we employ two widely known commercial large language models: OpenAI’s GPT-3.5 [4] and Google’s Bard [7]. We originally planned to include also an open-source alternative, Meta’s Llama 2 [17], but the model showed severe limitations in generating texts in our target languages, due to the training set being overwhelmingly (~90%) in English. Furthermore, even though not clearly prohibited,¹ use in languages other than English is considered ‘out-of-scope’.²

Like most LLMs, GPT-3.5 and Bard function according to a common logic, i.e., using transformers-based technology to mirror human language and produce textual responses to user inputs. They differ, however, in terms of neural network architecture, number of parameters, and training sets, whose details are not publicly disclosed due to concerns related to data privacy, intellectual property rights, and licensing. Options for user access and task automation also vary: OpenAI, for example, provides a paid API for its models, but as of now it is still limited to an improved version of GPT-3.5, whereas the web interface (ChatGPT) already features the follow-up model GPT-4. Bard, on the other side, provides no official API so far, so we had to resort to an unofficial Python package [10] to access it.

To iteratively generate plays, we devised a chain of prompts tailored to the specific features of each LLM we employed. In the case of GPT-3.5, we first set the *temperature* hyperparameter to 1.1 to boost the model’s creativity.³ Then, we took advantage of the recently implemented *messages* functions, which allowed us to give a *system-level instruction* shaping the model’s behaviour throughout the conversation.⁴ In other words, we set the chatbot persona to be more responsive to our prompts by issuing the instruction:

¹See <https://ai.meta.com/llama/use-policy>.

²See <https://huggingface.co/meta-llama/Llama-2-70b-chat-hf>.

³With the default value being 1 and the full range being 0-2.

⁴See <https://help.openai.com/en/articles/7042661-chatgpt-api-transition-guide>.

"You are a {language} playwright."

where 'language' is one of the three languages we use in our experiment (German, French, Russian). On the second step, we provided the model with a *starter prompt* to begin the exchange, as follows:

```
"Please write a first act of a 19th-century {language} play in the style
of {language} drama. Write it in {language}. The play must be in {language}.
{formatting_subprompt}"
```

The prompt was purposely redundant to force the model to write in the desired language, overriding the bias toward English generated by their training data and the prompt being in that language. Once we got a response from the model, we added it to a list storing the conversation history. We then sent the text back to the chatbot followed by what we called a *continuation prompt*, which looked like this:

```
"Please write another act of the same play. Write it in {language}.
The play must be in {language} in the style of a 19th-century play.
{formatting_subprompt}"
```

Notably, both the starter prompt and the continuation prompt featured a *formatting subprompt*. This is a purely technical typography instruction to enforce uniform textual formatting of a play, facilitating later conversion to TEI/XML. The formatting prompt was the following:

```
"Please print the character names in capital letters. Please put
stage directions in parentheses. After the stage direction,
insert a carriage return."
```

After the initial starter prompt, the system was fed with the continuation prompt four more times, resulting in generation of a five-act play saved as a single TXT file.

The pipeline employed for Bard was broadly similar, with some model-specific adjustments. First, the Google LLM does not allow the user to set a 'temperature' parameter to bolster creativity. As a consequence, the plays generated in the first tests were made up of few textual chunks insistently repeated scene after scene, with very little variability in terms of cast and plot. We compensated for this by adding another instruction to each prompt:

```
"Add some new characters and events. Remove some previous characters."
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The command was not always diligently executed by the model, and thus the result seemed to achieve the necessary balance between creativity and consistency. Furthermore, since the unofficial Bard API we used relies on user identification with an encrypted Google Account ID, the previous state of the dialogue did not have to be sent back to the model each time, as the web-service kept track of each session on the server side.

Figure 1: DraCor model card for our locally hosted corpus of LLM-generated plays, AIDraCor.

2.2 Metadata extraction

To extract structural features from the generated texts, we first processed them through *ezdrama*, a script which allows a quick conversion of plain text files into DraCor-compatible XMLs by applying a simple Markdown-like syntax [3]. We also manually post-corrected the XMLs to solve several textual problems, mainly related to speaker disambiguation, gender attribution, and scene segmentation, and removed English-language, non-diegetic material inserted by the models.⁵ We then mounted the plays in a dockerized DraCor instance [2], which enabled us to run the DraCor API metric service on a locally hosted corpus, AIDraCor (Figure 1).

At this point, by invoking a simple API call,⁶ we were able to extract all structural metadata the DraCor metric service can compute. We then proceed to remove some redundant features, either because they were pre-determined by the prompts (e.g. the number of acts, which was always capped at 5) or because they never appeared in the outputs (e.g. the number of verse lines, since all generated plays were in prose). Since the size of the generated plays was also determined by the models' limitation, some metrics related to speech distribution, such as the number of utterances or of speech directions, were not comparable with human texts in terms of absolute values. To allow some comparison, we calculated instead the ratio between them, which is size-independent. The measures we

⁵Bard, in particular, was often keen to make us aware of its 'creative' process, with detailed comments like: "In this act, I have added two new characters, CHARLES and MADAME DE SALLUST. [...] I have also changed the setting of the scene from a salon to a bedroom. The new characters add some conflict and suspense to the play. [...] The change in setting from a salon to a bedroom also adds some intimacy to the play. JEANNE is alone in her bedroom, and she is able to think more clearly about her decision. I hope you like this second act!"

⁶<https://dracor.org/doc/api#/public/corpus-metadata>.

eventually used for comparison with human-created plays are listed with a brief description in Table 1. Finally, we used the same method to obtain statistics for all plays available in the German, French, and Russian DraCor corpora which were written between 1800 and 1899.

Table 1: Overview of benchmark structural features extracted via DraCor API.

Feature	Type	Explanation
<code>num_of_segments</code>	size	number of subdivisions (scenes or acts) in the plays
<code>num_of_speakers</code>	size	number of characters with at least one utterance
<code>num_of_person_groups</code>	size	number of characters marked as groups (e.g. "Soldiers")
<code>ratio_sp</code>	speech distribution	percentage of characters' utterances on the total text tokens
<code>ratio_stage</code>	speech distribution	percentage of stage directions on the total text tokens
<code>average_degree</code>	network	average number of nodes to which a node is connected
<code>density</code>	network	ratio between the number of actual edges and the maximum number of possible edges
<code>average_clustering</code>	network	average of the local clustering coefficients of all the vertices
<code>max_degree</code>	network	maximum number of nodes to which a node is connected
<code>num_of_connected_components</code>	network	number of independent sub-graphs within the network
<code>diameter</code>	network	the longest shortest path between two nodes
<code>average_path_length</code>	network	average length of the shortest path that can be drawn between any two nodes

3 Findings and discussion

Table 2 shows the mean values of selected features in our nine corpora – three human-, six AI-generated. Results show how artificial plays stand out from the others in terms of size, partly because of the model's output constraints, but still retain 'realistic' network values. On average, both GPT-3.5 and Bard write short plays with a tight cast, resulting in a low number of edges but a density, clustering coefficient, and average path length comparable to texts in DraCor,

especially to French ones – the ones which are globally nearer to the ‘standard AI drama’.

Interestingly, all AI-generated texts exhibit an unusually high ratio of stage directions – three to four times more than in the benchmark corpora. Among other elements, this seems to confirm the suspicion that the model, despite being explicitly prompted to write a ‘19th-century’ drama, mostly drew upon more recent dramatic texts. A greater share of stage directions can indeed be considered distinctive of 20th-century theatre, where it signals the results of an ‘epification’ process ⁷ which has been already tracked in German and Russian literature [19] [15].

Table 2: Mean structural values for human- and AI-generated plays, rounded to the second decimal.

sample size	rus-dracor (211)	ger-dracor (629)	fre-dracor (1559)	rus-gpt (10)	ger-gpt (10)	fre-gpt (10)	rus-bard (10)	ger-bard (10)	fre-bard (10)
num_of_segments	25.73	28.37	9.0	10.5	5.4	8.1	4.9	10.1	9.4
num_of_speakers	16.29	25.44	7.09	8.0	6.1	6.9	7.1	6.9	5.8
num_of_speakers_male	11.29	17.68	2.88	2.8	3.7	3.9	4.7	5.2	3.4
num_of_speakers_female	4.07	5.26	1.45	1.2	2.0	2.7	2.1	1.2	1.9
num_of_speakers_unknown	0.93	2.5	2.76	0.0	0.4	0.3	0.2	0.0	0.4
num_of_person_groups	0.87	3.61	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.2	0.0	0.1
word_count_text	11252.56	17389.45	5929.31	963.9	1583.3	1561.3	1088.2	1671.2	1473.4
word_count_sp	10723.48	16507.82	5492.91	719.5	1049.9	919.5	842.0	1242.8	1053.6
word_count_stage	969.19	2030.08	247.6	311.2	551.8	665.5	297.4	488.6	396.8
average_degree	6.73	8.9	3.72	2.97	4.26	3.86	4.56	3.27	2.86
density	0.64	0.54	0.62	0.43	0.82	0.67	0.76	0.59	0.61
average_clustering	0.81	0.84	0.61	0.58	0.86	0.8	0.86	0.69	0.64
size	16.29	25.44	7.09	8.0	6.1	6.9	7.1	6.9	5.8
max_degree	11.72	18.53	5.36	6.0	5.1	5.7	6.1	5.6	4.6
num_connected_components	1.36	1.24	1.09	1.4	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.1	1.0
num_edges	80.5	152.84	29.95	13.1	14.1	13.7	16.5	12.9	8.5
diameter	2.38	2.64	1.36	2.3	1.9	2.1	2.0	2.0	2.0
average_path_length	1.41	1.54	0.96	1.54	1.18	1.35	1.24	1.36	1.41
ratio_sp	0.95	0.95	0.93	0.75	0.66	0.59	0.77	0.74	0.72
ratio_stage	0.09	0.12	0.04	0.32	0.35	0.43	0.27	0.29	0.27

Moreover, by considering the features of human- and AI-generated plays as vectors, we were also able to compute Euclidean distance between texts and thus find out which human-written dramas were most similar to the GPT-3.5 and Bard outputs. Unsurprisingly, they are short, basic plays with a limited number of nodes and edges, often belonging to theatrical subgenres, as the following list shows:

- Most ‘GPT-like’ French play ⁸: *L’Habit Vert* (1849), a *proverbe* ⁹ by Alfred de Musset and Émile Augier

⁷According to [19], stage directions in classical theatre mostly served as introductory remarks or practical cues, while ‘epified’ stage directions – from Brecht onwards – became a further channel of expression for the narrator’s voice, growing in number and extension.

⁸Interestingly, the French texts most similar to GPT outputs were actually a couple of translations from Sophocles and Eschylus by Leconte de Lisle. Since the textual structure mirrored the Greek originals, however, we didn’t consider them as truly ‘French texts’, and we skipped over to Musset and Augier.

⁹Short, mundane genre born in the 17th century and later revived by Musset. See <https://www.cnrtl.fr/definition/academie9/proverbe>.

- Most 'Bard-like' French play: *Aldo le Rimeur* (1833), a two-act comedy by George Sand
- Most 'GPT-like' German play: *Die Wette* (1812), a *Lustspiel* by Johann W. Goethe
- Most 'Bard-like' German play: *Herr und Sklave* (1834), a short tragedy by Joseph Christian von Zedlitz
- Most 'GPT-like' Russian play: *Светский случай* (*Svetskij sluchaj*, 1826), a one-act piece by Nikolai Khmel'nitsky
- Most 'Bard-like' Russian play: *Опрометчивый Турка, или: Приятно ли быть внуком?* (*Oprometchivyy Turka, ili: Prijatno li byt' vnukom?*, 1863), an absurdist play by Kozma Prutkov

Ultimately, the little experiment we conducted here was able to offer a first look into the morphology of LLM-generated texts. The findings suggest that when the models are allowed to write autonomously, they tend to generate what can be described as 'situational dialogues,' consisting of several scenes featuring a limited number of recurring characters and low network values. The requirement of crafting dramatic works in a certain style (in our case, that of a 19th-century play) seems not to have prompted them to devise more intricate characters and plots, as those displayed by historical drama of the time.

In future developments, we aim at improving the text generation pipeline through more advanced fine-tuning of prompts and parameters, trying to find the most efficient approach for imitating age-specific playwriting conventions and overcoming the models' 'modernity bias'. Addressing the challenges posed by Llama and deploying it successfully alongside other open-source models would also improve the depth of the investigation. Eventually, our structure-oriented approach might be complemented by content-aware computational approaches, like topic modelling or stylometry,¹⁰ which would allow for a deeper understanding of the LLMs' text generation capabilities from a literary perspective.

4 Code availability

Scripts used for text generation and analysis, together with the 60 AI-written plays, are available in this repository: <https://github.com/lucagiovannini7/artificial-dramas>.

¹⁰A recent paper by [11] has tested the ability of GPT-3 to deceive stylometric verification in authorship attribution, but without further commenting on the generated texts' style.

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